

Assessment of Solid Waste Generation of the Health Facilities and its Management–in Mathura City

Paper Id : 18923 Submission Date : 09/05/2024 Acceptance Date : 23/05/2024 Publication Date : 25/05/2024

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.12531165

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Abstract

In the urban areas the growth of population is very high due to high birth rate and low death rate. Low death rate is the result of the development of the health facilities. These health facilities are developing day by day in urban areas. These facilities are generating the solid waste in a large scale. These facilities have not disposal and treatment technologies for reduce, recycle and reuse of its. Hospitals, clinics, dispensary and pathology centers are the main sources of solid waste generation in the health facilities. These facilities are generating such types of solid waste regularly. Due to poor management of the solid waste in health facilities the problems of environmental degradation and health issues are increasing in urban areas.

Keywords

Health Facilities, Environmental Degradation, Solid Waste, Generation, Management.

Introduction

Healthcare facilities are generating different types of wastes. These facilities are generating hazardous and non-hazardous waste. Hazardous waste is a special type of waste which if not properly treated can pose a risk to human health and to the environment. It is estimated that almost 15% of the total amount of produced medical waste is hazardous and can be infectious, toxic or radioactive. Such types of waste contains potentially harmful micro organisms that can be spread among healthcare personnel, hospitals, patients and the general public, causing serious illness. Medical waste is very harmful to the environment and human health. Different types of chemical are used to investigate the diseases by the pathologies labs. Infectious syringe are harmful for the human beings, animals and birds etc. Environment is suffering from the air, water and soil pollution by the untreated health facilities wastes.

Hospitals, clinics, nursing homes, pathology labs etc. are the main sources of medical waste generation. Cotton, clothes, plastics, paper, board, wood, metals, human organs, polythene, glass, waste food etc. are contained the medical waste. Degradable and non-degradable wastes is generated by the health facilities. Mostly health facilities have not treatment technology of solid waste management. These health facilities collected it from the campus of hospitals and the campus of health facilities. Bio-degradable and non-biodegradable wastes is generated by the health facilities. Very few health facilities have facilities of segregation of waste and disposal of waste. Mostly health facilities use rickshaw and van to transport it and deposited it. Recycling technologies is not developed in the study area for the treatment of the medical waste. High standard health facilities are more responsible to increase the medical waste because these facilities provide the standard quality of medical services and focused on cleaning. So such types of health facilities are generating the solid waste.

Objective of study

To complete the present study the researcher has selected the following objectives–

1. To analyse the sources of solid waste generation of the health facilities of the study area.
2. To analyse the generation of the solid waste of the health facilities in the study area.

3. To analyse the impacts of medical waste on environment in the study area.

Review of Literature

Many research scholars has completed his research work on the impacts of healthcare facilities solid wastes. They examined the impacts of medical wastes on environment and human health. The researcher has made an attempt to arrange the literature related to the research problem. The review of literature related to the research problem is given as–

Radha, Kalaivani and Lavanya (2009) completed a research paper on 'A case study of biomedical waste management.' They analysed that inadequate management of biomedical waste can be associated with risk to healthcare workers, patients, communities and their environment. They analysed that mostly hospitals have not treatment technologies to dispose the medical waste. This is the result of lack of education, awareness and trained personnel to manage the waste in the hospitals. They have not proper funds to management the medical waste. Stephen and Elijah (2011) presented a research paper on 'Healthcare waste management in Nigeria– A case study.' They examined that healthcare waste constitutes a special category of waste because they contain potentially harmful materials. They found that healthcare facilities waste management is a serious problem in developing countries. They found that healthcare facilities was generated 0.62 kg/person/day and 0.81 kg/bed/day waste in Nigeria. They found the level of waste management in zero out of 10. Umar and Yahaya (2014) presented a research paper on 'Hospital waste management practices – A case study of primary health care centers in Fagge local government area', Kano state. They examined the hospitals waste management techniques. They defined the different sources of the solid waste generation of the healthcare facilities. Due to population growth the healthcare facilities are developing and these facilities are generating the solid waste in a high level amount. Javid and Manoj (2019) completed his research paper on 'Impact of biomedical waste on environment and human health.' They analysed the impact of biomedical waste on human health and analysed the diseases which are generated by the biomedical waste. Asthama, cancer, neurological disorders, allergies etc. are the main diseases which are generated by the medical waste. Biomedical also degraded the environment and reduced the quality of water, air and soil. Ravi and Rampal (2019) presented a research paper on 'Biomedical waste generation composition and management – A case study of Shree Maharaja Gulab Singh Hospital Shalamar, Jammu.' In their research paper they analysed that according to the biomedical waste rule 2016 the four coloured dustbins are used to depositing the biomedical waste. Staff, Patients and attendants of patients have not knowledge about the B.M.W. rules 2016. They analysed that in this hospital every bed is generating 116.37 gram biomedical waste per day. Every department have different amount of waste of generation in this hospital. Altaf (2019) presented a research paper on 'Healthcare waste management.' They analysed the types of healthcare wastes, segregation of healthcare waste, recycling of healthcare waste and waste minimization. They suggested that waste minimization is the first and most important step in healthcare waste management. Elsayed, Ibrahim and Gehan (2020) analysed about the hospital waste management system. They analysed the healthcare waste management policy. They discussed 8 stages of hospital waste management–waste minimization, waste generation, segregation and containerization, collection, transport, treatment and final disposal. Ilyas, S. Srivastava, R.R. Kim, H. (2020) presented a research paper on 'Disinfection technology and strategies for covid-19 hospital and biomedical waste management.' Healthcare waste generation in China (Wuhan) increased significantly from 40 tons to 240 tons per day. Singh, Ogunseitan and Tang (2022) presented a research paper on 'Medical waste: current challenges and future opportunities for sustainable management.' They analysed that all countries are facing the problems of medical waste management. They examined that an average of 38.9% of medical waste was segregated for proper management and only 41% of workers were trained in service for medical waste disposal. They analysed that 35% plastics materials is used in healthcare facilities. Chahal and Chahal (2023) present a research paper on "The medical waste management issues, challenges and solution in India perspective." They analysed that healthcaer sector in India is developing very fast and becoming the pillar of the economy. It is a big source of employment, revenue and the solid waste generation. Waste management is one of the crucial issues affecting this sector is growth.

Methodology

Data Base

To complete the present study the researcher has used both types of data. Primary data has been collected by the sample survey of the health facilities. Secondary data has been collected from the statistical magazine of district Mathura health facilities records (Hospitals) and differents websites.

Research Methodology

To complete the present study the researcher has used statistical methods to find out the result to analyse the data the researcher has used tabulation, graphical and non-graphical methods. Personal interview method is used to collect the primary data by the using of the questionnaire.

Sampling

To complete the present study the researcher has made an attempt to collect the primary data related to the research problem by using the following research design–

Health Facilities	No. of Sample	Category	Sample Collection Days
Hospitals	03	1. High Scale Hospitals 2. Medium Scale Hospitals 3. Low Scale Hospitals	30
Nursing Home	03	1. High Scale Nursing Home 2. Medium Scale Nursing Home 3. Low Scale Nursing Home	30
Clinics	03	1. High Scale Clinic 2. Medium Scale Clinic 3. Low Scale Clinic	30
Pathology Labs	03	1. High Scale Pathology Lab 2. Medium Scale Pathology Lab 3. Low Scale Pathology Lab	30
Total	12	12	-

To complete the present study the researcher has used the above mentioned research design. The researcher has selected 12 health facilities to collect the solid waste from the study area. These health facilities are selected by using the randomly sampling method. These health facilities are divided into 3 category high, medium and low.

Analysis

Study Area:–

Mathura city is selected to complete the present study. It is situated in western Uttar Pradesh. It is the headquarter of district Mathura. It is located at 27.49° latitude and 77.67° longitude. It has covered 75.04 km² geographical area (2001). It is situated at Yamuna River Bank.

Statement of the Research Problem:–

Health facilities are generating the solid waste at alarming rate in the study area. They have not solid waste management to reduce, reuse sense and recycling it. So mostly health facilities transported it and deposited it an open areas. So many gases are generating on the depositing sites and mosquitoes, flies and insects are speared the different types of diseases. So the problem of environmental degradation is rising there very fast rate. Due to very poor management technology in health facilities the solid waste amount is increasing day by day.

Sources of Generation of Solid Waste:–

A lot of sources are present in the study area which are generating the solid waste. Residential area, streets, roads, daily markets, construction sites, hotels, industries,

restaurant, marriage halls, offices, institution and health facilities etc. are the main sources of solid waste generation. The researcher has selected only health facilities to analyse the solid waste generation. Different types of health facilities are present here. Hospitals, clinics, dispensary, nursing homes, pathology labs etc. are main health facilities which are generating a huge amount of solid waste. Health facilities of the study area are given below in the table–

Table–1

Availability of the Health Facilities in the Study Area Mathura City (2022)

S.No.	Health Facilities	No. of Units	Percentage
1.	Allopathic Hospitals	03	14.28
2.	Community Health Center	01	4.76
3.	Primary Health Center	09	42.86
4.	Aayurvedic Hospitals	03	14.29
5.	Homeopathic Hospitals	03	14.29
6.	Family and Mother Child Welfare Center	02	9.52
Total		21	100

Source: District statistical magazine of Mathura district, year 2022.

According to the above table, we analysed that 21 health facilities are present here under the authority of government. According to 2022 year there are present 3 allopathic hospitals, 1 community health center, 9 primary health center, 3 aayurvedic hospitals, 3 homeopathic hospitals and 2 family and mother child welfare centers. These facilities are unable to provide the health facilities of the population of Mathura city 4.81 Lac. Although private health facilities are developing here but due to costly treatment in private health facilities poor people are unable to take facilities. These government and private health facilities are generating the solid waste regularly in the study area. Such types of solid waste generating the health issues in the study area. This solid waste is depositing outside the city and creating the environmental problems.

Generation of The Solid Waste by the Health Facilities:–

These health facilities are playing an important role to generating the solid waste in the study area. Hospitals and nursing homes are a large producer of the solid waste. The researcher has made an attempt to collect the data of solid waste from the health facilities. To collect the primary data of solid waste from the health facilities the researcher has selected 12 health facilities. 30 days solid waste is collected from the sample health facilities by the researcher. These health facilities generated different types of solid waste. The details of solid waste which is generated by the health facilities is given below in the table–

Table–2

Generated of the solid waste by the health facilities in the study area Mathura city (2023)

S. No.	Health Facilities	Units	Generated Solid Waste by Health Facilities (in kg)			Total (in kg)
			Small	Medium	Large	
1.	Hospital	03	535.5	742.50	1215.0	2493.00

2.	Nursing Home	03	457.5	615.0	922.50	1995.00
3.	Clinics	03	375.0	420.0	670.0	1465.00
4.	Pathology Labs	03	385.5	405.0	750.0	1540.50
Total		12	1753.5	2182.50	3557.5	7493.50

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of sample survey November 2023.

According to the above table, we found that 12 health facilities generated 7493.50 kg solid waste in November 2023 in the study area. Small scale hospital generated 535.5 kg solid waste, medium scale hospital generated 742.50 kg solid waste and large scale hospital generated 1215.0 kg solid waste in November 2023 in Mathura city. Large scale hospital is more generator of solid waste than the small scale hospital. These 3 (small, medium and large scale) hospitals generated 2493.0 kg solid waste in November 2023 in the study area. Small nursing home generated 457.5 kg solid waste, medium scale nursing home generated 615.0 kg solid waste and large scale nursing home generated 922.50 kg solid waste in November 2023 in the study area. These three nursing home generated 1995.0 kg solid waste in the study area in a month. Clinics generated 1465.0 kg solid waste in November 2023 in the study area. Small scale clinics generated 375.0 kg, medium scale clinics generated 420.0 kg, and large scale clinics generated 670.0 kg solid waste in the study area. Pathology labs generated 1540.50 kg solid waste in November 2023 in the study area. Small scale pathology lab generated 385.5 kg solid waste, medium scale pathology lab generated 405.0 kg solid waste and large scale pathology lab generated 750.0 kg solid waste in November 2023 in Mathura city. On the basis of the above table we can say that these health facilities are generating solid waste regularly. Large scale health facilities are generating more solid waste than the small scale health facilities. Large scale health facilities have standard quality in using the health care items and such types of health facilities focus on health and cleaning the campus.

Composition of Medical Solid Waste:-

Different types of items are used in medical facilities during the period of medical treatment plastics, needles, papers, glass, cotton, clothes etc. are main items. Medical solid waste contains papers, plastics, cotton, glass, clothes, metals, board, wood, waste food, human organs etc. It is estimated that 15% of the total amount of produced health care facilities is hazardous waste and 85% waste is non hazardous waste. Medical solid waste contains potentially harmful microorganism that can be spread among healthcare personnel, hospital patients and the general public causing serious illness. The composition of medical solid waste is given below in the table-

Table-3

Composition of the Medical Solid Waste in the Mathura City (2023)

S. No.	Waste Components	Sampling Sites Percentage				
		Hospital	Nursing Home	Clinics	Pathology Lab	Average
1.	Cotton waste	28.50	30.80	30.70	27.50	29.38
2.	Plastic waste	25.60	26.50	28.30	28.00	27.10
3.	Paper waste	17.25	16.40	18.25	18.40	17.58
4.	Rubber waste	1.10	1.00	1.50	2.00	1.40
5.	Food waste	12.40	10.40	6.60	7.50	9.23
6.	Glass waste	2.80	1.70	2.60	4.40	2.87

7.	Cardboard waste	2.50	2.20	1.80	1.10	1.90
8.	Inert material waste	3.80	3.20	2.70	2.25	2.98
9.	Radioactive waste	1.25	1.40	1.10	2.15	1.48
10.	Metallic waste	2.10	2.60	2.20	2.25	2.28
11.	Miscellaneous waste	2.70	3.80	4.25	4.45	3.80
Total		100	100	100	100	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of sample survey, November 2023.

According to the above table, we found that medical solid waste contains cotton waste 29.38%, plastics waste 27.10%, paper waste 17.58%, rubber waste 1.40%, food waste 9.23%, glass waste 2.87%, cardboard waste 1.90%, inert medical waste 2.98%, radioactive waste 1.48%, metallic waste 2.28% and miscellaneous waste 3.80%. In the sample survey we found that the solid waste of hospital contained cotton waste 28.50%, plastic waste 25.60%, paper waste 17.25%, rubber waste 1.10%, food waste 12.40%, glass waste 2.80%, cardboard waste 2.50%, inert material waste 3.80%, radioactive waste 1.25%, metallic waste 2.10% and miscellaneous waste 2.70%. From nursing home solid waste we found cotton waste 30.80%, plastic waste 26.50%, paper waste 16.40%, rubber waste 1.00%, food waste 10.40%, glass waste 1.70%, cardboard waste 2.20%, inert material waste 3.20%, radioactive waste 1.40%, metallic waste 2.60% and miscellaneous waste 3.80%. From the clinics solid waste we found cotton waste 30.70%, plastic waste 28.30%, 18.25%, rubber waste 1.50%, food waste 6.60%, glass waste 2.60%, cardboard waste 1.80%, inert material waste 2.70%, radioactive waste 1.10%, metallic waste 2.20% and miscellaneous waste 4.25%. In pathology labs solid waste we found cotton waste 27.50%, plastics waste 28.00%, paper waste 18.40%, rubber waste 2.00%, food waste 7.50%, glass waste 4.40%, cardboard waste 1.10%, inert materials waste 2.25%, radioactive waste 2.15%, metallic waste 2.25% and miscellaneous waste 4.45%. So we can say that different types of medical facilities generate different types of solid waste.

Impacts of Medical Solid Waste on Environment:-

At present medical waste is a big challenge to environment and human health. Medical wastes contain hazardous substances such as chemicals, medications, radioactive material that can contaminate soils, waster bodies and the air if not properly disposed of. HIV hepatitis B and C are the 3 most commonly spread viruses worldwide due to improper treatment of medical wastes. They are transmitted through injuries from contaminated syringes and needles, doctors, nurse and sanitation workers are amongst the most vulnerable to the harmful effects of medical waste. These medical wastes generate-lungs infections, skin infections, cholera, tuberculosis hepatitis B and C etc. are the main impacts of the medical untreated wastes on human health. Its lead to the spread of infectious diseases. Medical wastes also increase the problem of soil, air and water pollution. Different types of chemicals which is used in the healthcare facilities are responsible to increase the toxics in the environment. Impacts of medical wastes on human health and environment are given below-

- i. Medical untreated wastes reduced the quality of air and water.
- ii. Its increased the infectious diseases and effected the human organs such as lungs, liver and kidney etc.
- iii. Its reduced the harmful gases and degraded the environment.
- iv. Poor management medical wastes contributed to the spread of infectious diseases especially through animals and insects that come into contact with these wastes.
- v. Medical wastes generated different types of insects, which are responsible to increase the diseases like that cholera and malaria etc.

Management of Medical Solid Wastes:-

Untreated medical solid waste is creating the environmental degradation and human health issues. Air and water pollution is increasing day by day. Infectious diseases are increasing regularly. Respiratory and lungs diseases are increasing due to increasing the medical solid wastes. Animals are eating such types of medical wastes and getting unhealthy and loosing immunity. So the cattle are dying in a large scale. Infectious wastes, pathological wastes, sharps wastes, chemical wastes, pharmaceutical wastes genotoxic wastes, radioactive wastes and non hazardous wastes etc. are the medical wastes. These wastes are generated from the hospitals, nursing homes, clinics, diagnostic research and laboratory centers, blood banks, mortuary centers, animal research centers, rehabilitative centers and pathology centers. We need to healthcare waste management practices because the medical wastes is increasing day by day and medical facilities have not suitable treatment technology of the wastes. In the observation we found that lack of awareness of health hazards related to healthcare waste, lack of training about the proper waste disposal practices, disposal system unavailable, lack of awareness about the harmful/impacts of medical wastes. Poor funds etc. are increasing the problems of medical wastes in the study area. The researcher has made an attempt to management the healthcare facilities wastes. Some steps are essential to management the medical wastes. Which are as-

- Step-I ® Survey of waste generated sources
- Step-II ® Segregation of hospital wastes
- Step-III ® Collection and categorization of wastes
- Step-IV ® Storages of the waste for a very short periods
- Step-V ® Transportation of the wastes
- Step-VI ® Treatment of the wastes

We can use different colours bins to management the healthcare facilities wastes.

The following methods will be helpful to disposal the healthcare facilities wastes-

Incineration
Autoclaving
Microwaving
Chemicals

Conclusion

Healthcare facilities are essential to control the diseases and provide the good health and long life for the people. These facilities are developing rapidly in the study area. These healthcare facilities are generating a large amount of solid wastes in the study area. Hospitals, nursing homes, clinics, pathology labs, blood bank and mortuary etc. are the main sources of solid wastes generators of the healthcare facilities.

On the basis of the sample survey of 12 healthy facilities generated 7493.50 kg solid wastes in November 2023 in the study area Mathura city. 3 hospitals generated 2493.00 kg solid waste, 3 nursing homes generated 1995.00 kg solid wastes, 3 clinics generated 1465.00 kg solid wastes and 3 pathology labs generated 1540.50 kg solid wastes in November 2023 in the study area. In the observation of the medical solid wastes contain cotton waste 29.38%, plastics waste 27.10%, paper waste 17.58%, rubber waste 1.40%, food waste 9.23%, glass water 2.87%, cardboard waste 1.90%, inert-material waste 2.98%, radioactive waste 1.48%, metallic waste 2.28% and miscellaneous waste 3.80%. Such

types of material which is generated by the medical facilities have different amount of the medical wastes and materials.

Suggestions for the future Study Wastages of healthcare facilities is increased the problems of environmental degradation and adverse impacts on human health. These healthcare facilities are developing day by day but have not management techniques to disposal of the medical wastage. These untreated wastes can be created dangerous problems for the human beings and environment. So some steps are essential to control the generation of solid waste and management of its. These are given as–

1. Different types of medical wastes should be collected into the different colours dustbin.
2. After collection of the medical wastes should be transported within 24 hours at the disposal sites.
3. Segregation techniques should be used to control the dissolve of harmful chemical into the air and water.
4. Medical wastes should be deposited and treated outside of the city.
5. Recycling techniques should be used to control the increasing of the medical wastes.
6. Bio-degradable medical wastes should be treated as manner to fertile the land and growing the crops.
7. Non-biodegradable medical wastes should be treated as reduce and recycling methods.
8. Medical wastes generation data should be maintained by the every healthcare facilities to management its.

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